

THE IMPACT OF BANK CREDIT ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY - AN APPLIED STUDY ON THE LIBYAN ECONOMY DURING THE PERIOD (1990-2023)

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Abstract

This research aimed to measure the impact of credit on GDP at constant prices in the Libyan economy during the period (1990-2023), and using the Johansen Co-integration method, and relying on the standard statistical program (STATA15), the research found a weak correlation between the two research variables, in addition to the existence of a long-term joint integration relationship between the two variables, and it was also found that positive changes in bank credit exert a positive impact on the average per capita GDP in the long term, while negative changes in bank credit exert no significant impact on the average GDP per capita in Libya, as well as the Pairwise Granger Causality Tests indicated a causal relationship compatible with economic theory from credit (TC) to output (GDPPC).

Keywords: Bank Credit, GDP Per Capita, Economic Activity, Joint Integration, Loans.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bank credit is one of the most important financing tools that are used by all countries of the world with different degrees of progress in financing development programs, and bridging the gap between savings and local investments, and credit policies in Libya are linked to the objectives of general economic policies (Central Bank of Libya, 2023), represented in achieving economic stability and financial soundness, and economic growth, especially diversifying sources of income, as the value of loans granted witnessed a development throughout the study period, reaching the year 1990 valued at 3053.3 million dinars and reached 28510.4 million dinars in 2023. Theories, experiments, and scientific evidence from most previous studies have proven the difference in the standard methodology used, as some of them will be listed later, about the existence of a positive linear relationship between credit and GDP, the difference was in the degree of response of economic activity to changes in credit, some studies have indicated a weak impact of credit on output, and others have a strong effect, so this topic was addressed for study by the researcher, to research the degree of response in the Libyan economy to credit During the period of study. This paper attempts to answer the following question: What is the impact of bank credit on the average GDP per capita at constant prices in the Libyan economy during the period 1990-2023, and in the Libyan economy during the period 1990-2023? The research is based on the hypothesis that there is a direct impact of credit on GDP at constant prices, using per capita output as an indicator of output, and this study aims to test the validity of the hypothesis based on the descriptive approach in collecting

study data, and to conduct a test of the validity of the study hypothesis, and to achieve this goal the research was divided in addition to the introduction as follows:

The general framework of the study. - Previous studies. - Evolution of bank credit growth and per capita output in Libya during the period 1990-2023. - Practical framework of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bank credit plays a pivotal role in shaping economic activity, particularly in developing and transition economies. Understanding the nature and extent of this relationship is essential for policymakers, financial institutions, and researchers seeking to boost economic growth through effective financial intermediation. A growing body of empirical literature has examined the impact of bank credit on various aspects of economic performance, with mixed results across countries, periods, and methodology. This literature review explores several studies that have investigated the relationship between bank credit and economic growth in different national contexts, including Libya, Iraq, Mexico, and selected European countries. The review highlights key findings, methodological approaches, and nuances of the results, ranging from positive short- and long-term relationships to weak or insignificant effects, thus providing a comprehensive foundation for future research in this area.

Al-Tallawy (2023) aims to identify the extent of the impact of bank credit on economic activity in Libya during the period 1970-2022, using annual data for both economic activity represented by GDP (economic growth) and bank credit for commercial banks, and the study relied on the methodology of joint integration in the Engle and Granger method and on the Granger causality test. Causality Granger The results of the study showed that there is no long-term relationship between bank credit and the volume of economic growth, but in the short term, the results based on the Granger causality test found a positive two-way causal relationship between bank credit and economic growth.

Murad and Faraj (2023) examine the impact of the relationship between bank credit and GDP and showed that it is positive, moral and compatible with the foundations of economic theory, as the higher the volume of bank credit and loans granted by commercial banks, the different economic sectors increase the volume of investment and thus the GDP rises. The result of flexibility showed that the higher the bank credit by 1%, the higher the GDP by 83%, which is a weak percentage, meaning that the output does not respond to the increase in bank credit at high rates despite the rise in bank credit, and the reason for this is due to the inefficient use in industrial, agricultural and service projects with economic and financial feasibility.

Hussein (2022) measured the impact of bank credit on economic growth in the Libyan economy during the period 1990-2019 Using the autoregressive model for nonlinear distributed slowdown periods NARDL, the research reached several results that can be summarized in the existence of weak linear correlation between the two research variables, in addition to the existence of a common integration relationship between these two variables, and it was also found that positive changes in bank credit exert a positive impact on economic growth in the short and long term, while negative changes in credit are not exercised. Banker has little impact

on Libya's economic growth. Khalid (2023) aims to identify the reality and reality of bank credit and then analyze the gross domestic product and the foreign trade sector in Iraq, as well as the statement of the impact of bank credit on the gross domestic product and the foreign trade sector in Iraq. The research problem revolves around the statement of the impact of bank credit on GDP and the foreign trade sector. Which of the two variables was the most influential bank credit during the study period (2005-2021), and the research starts from the hypothesis that bank credit had a positive or negative role in the GDP and the foreign trade sector, and to reach the research methodology, the researcher used the descriptive analytical method. It was concluded that bank credit has a very important role, especially in increasing GDP and financing the foreign trade sector and that the relationship between bank credit, GDP and the foreign trade sector (exports and imports) is a direct relationship, as the increase in granting bank credit and lending operations by banks to economic activities and sectors leads to an increase in GDP and stimulate the foreign trade sector.

Rodríguez (2022) estimates the impact of commercial bank credit, in the case of Mexico, on economic activity in the entire manufacturing sector, and seven selected industrial sectors. Contrary to the literature that has examined the effects of bank credit on the Mexican economy, this research finds evidence (through ARDL border models) of a positive and significant impact of bank credit on production in the entire sector and the following sectors: 1) Food, 2) Beverage and tobacco, 3) Paper, 4) Non-metallic metal products, and 5) Manufacturing of transportation equipment; coupled with significant effects of fixed investment in machinery and equipment, the real interest rate. In addition, we found no evidence that the concentration of loans affects industrial production. Based on these findings, this study assumes that bank credit is important as a catalyst for industrial activity, and it would be useful to design policies that promote and deepen these effects. Korkmaz (2015) examined whether domestic loans created by the banking sector had any impact on macroeconomic variables such as inflation and economic growth of ten selected European countries by analyzing panel data. Annual data was used for the period from 2006 to 2012. As a result of the analysis of the panel data, it was established that the domestic loans created by the banking sector for ten European countries did not affect inflation but affected economic growth.

Agnes. et al, (2019) contributes to the debate by assessing the impact of bank credit on economic activity using data from a developing economy. The study period ranged from January 2007 to December 2017. Estimates resulting from descriptive statistics show that the activity of the economy and bank credit chains is characterized by negative and peak deviation, with abnormal distribution. The results extracted from Dickey's enhanced unitary root test show that all variables are unstable in level, but after the first difference, the variables became stable and included in the degree The results from the multiple regression model show that bank credit has a positive and significant impact on economic activity. Thus, we conclude that bank credit has a predictive effect on economic activity. One of the results of this conclusion is that regulators in the banking system must develop policies that enhance access to credit for the private sector while containing inflation.

Research Gap

Several studies have explored similar objectives and hypotheses but employed different regression models. For instance, Hawij (2022) utilized the autoregressive model for nonlinear distributed lag periods (NARDL), while Rubén (2023) relied on the ARDL autoregressive model. Korkmaz (2015) applied the Panel Data model, demonstrating that domestic loans from the banking sector in ten European countries did not impact inflation but did affect economic growth. Abdul Razzaq Al-Talawi (2022) employed a joint integration methodology based on Engle and Granger's approach and utilized Granger's causality test. In contrast, Khalid Hussain (2023) used relative scale and growth rate, and Milad (2023) applied the ordinary least squares method. Additionally, a study by Agnes A. Ogwang et al. (2019) found that bank credit has a predictive effect on economic activity. This diversity in methodologies highlights a research gap that warrants further investigation. Research that contrasts with the findings of Tallawy's study (2023) indicated that there is no long-term relationship between bank credit and the level of economic growth. The reviewed studies did not use per capita income, which is more comprehensive and reveals the true state of the economy in terms of citizens' living standards, according to Todaro and Smith (2002). Finally, this study seeks to address the aforementioned shortcomings by examining the impact of bank credit on Libya's economic activity. Thus, the impact of bank credit on economic activity will be studied and applied to the Libyan economy during the period (1990-2023).

Evolution of credit growth and average growth of GDP per capita at constant prices in Libya during the period 1990-2023:

Table 1: Evolution of credit growth and per capita growth %

Year	per capita growth %	Credit Growth %	Year	per capita growth%	Credit Growth %
1990	0.13	0.16	2007	0	0
1991	0.27	0.29	2008	0.11	0.03
1992	-0.30	0.12	2009	0.06	0.08
1993	0.24	0.10	2010	-0.10	0.09
1994	-0.36	-0.02	2011	-0.07	0.07
1995	0.92	0.24	2012	-0.11	0.07
1996	-0.19	0.15	2013	0.09	-0.09
1997	-0.24	0.09	2014	0.10	0.06
1998	-0.15	0.01	2015	-0.11	0.09
1999	0.02	-0.07	2016	0.32	0.15
2000	0.35	-0.07	2017	0.06	0.07
2001	0.14	-0.06	2018	-0.11	0.08
2002	-0.06	0.03	2019	-0.40	0.05
2003	-0.09	0.00	2020	0.28	0.07
2004	-0.27	0.16	2021	0.26	-0.04
2005	0.17	0.17	2022	0.43	-0.05
2006	-0.10	0.24	2023	0.27	0.15

Source: World Bank.

Source: Central Bank of Libya - Consolidated Balance Sheet of Commercial Banks.

It is clear from Table (1) and Figure (1) (2) that there is a weak, confused and irregular relationship between credit growth and GDP per capita growth at constant prices, while credit-positive changes for some years (1991 - 1999 - 2003 - 2008 - 2012 - 2022), have a positive impact on the growth of GDP per capita at constant prices, and the rest of the years negative changes in credit do not affect the growth of GDP per capita at constant prices.

Figure 1

Figure 2

3. EMPIRICAL METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to measure the impact of bank credit (loans) on GDP per capita at constant prices in Libya using time series analysis.

The study form can be formulated with the following equation:

$$GDPPC = f(TC)$$

Rewriting the equation gives us the following standard form:

$$GDPPC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TC_t + U_t \quad (1)$$

where:

$GDPPC$ = Per Capita Gross Domestic Product , and

MS = Bank credit

Given that the macroeconomic variables selected are likely to have nonlinear relationships, the two variables were converted to linear form by taking the values of the natural logarithm. The logarithmic form of the econometric model is as follows:

$$\ln (GDPPC_t) = \ln(\beta_0) + \beta_1 \ln (TC)_t + U_t \quad (2)$$

To follow the recommended procedures to estimate this regression, it is necessary to ensure that the model variables are static first, and then use a Grogery hansen Cointegration Test to determine the existence of integration between the variables. If we observe that there is cointegration between the variables and that they are first-order integral, the parameters of equation No. 2 can be estimated through one of the integration regression methods, where we propose the fully modified least squares (FMOLS) method. Therefore, the steps that we will follow in our standard analysis after testing the unit root of the time series and then testing the existence of a long-term relationship between the variables under study using the cointegration test, and then rely in our analysis on the (FMOLS) to estimate the long-term relationship between the variables. This is because FMOLS uses a semi-parametric correction - To get rid of the problems caused by the long relationship between the variables under study, and thus provides unbiased estimates. Our selection of FMOLS for this study is therefore appropriate.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Correlation tests:

Table 2: Correlation between independent variables

Variable	GDPPC	TC
GDPPC	1	0.12
TC	0.12	1

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

From the previous analysis of Table (2), it can be seen that there is a weak correlation between credit and economic activity.

As mentioned earlier, before starting the estimation process, we make sure that the model variables are static, as testing the roots of the unit using the Dickey-Fuller and Philip Perron test indicates that all variables were not stable in their level, but rather settled at the first difference. Thus all variables are integrated I (1).

4.2 Unit Root Tests (ADF & PP)

In ADF tests, it was found that the time series of the bank credit variable and GDP are unstable over time at this level. However, after converting and taking the first differences and including the constant and constant directionally, these chains showed stability over time in the first difference.

For P tests, the results of the unit-roots did not differ from the previous results. The time series of the variables studied showed instability at the level, but once converted to the first differences, it became stationary. Thus all variables are integrated at first-order I(1).

Table 3: Unit Root Test with Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test					
Variable	Level		First difference		
Probability	Prob		Prob		
Vector	Int. Single vector	Int.+ T trend and constant vector	Int. Single vector	Int.+ T trend and constant vector	Degree of integration
LGDPPC	0.0093.	0.0699.	0.0000.	0.0000.	I(1)
LTC	0.9616.	0.7583.	0.0219.	0.0129	I(1)

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

Table 4: Unit root test using the Phillips Perron test - PP)

Phillips Perron – PP test					
Variable	Level		First difference		
Probability	Prob		Prob		
Vector	Int. Single vector	Int.+ T trend and constant vector	Int. Single vector	Int.+ T trend and constant vector	Degree of integration
LGDPPC	0.7588	0.6854	0.0452	0.1848	I(1)
LTC	0.9438	0.502.	0.0212	0.0100	I(1)

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

4.3 The optimal lag:

The optimal slowdown period should be determined before assessing the long-term relationship, either in the long or short term. This is done to avoid measurement errors by using different tests for slowdown intervals for the same equations and the same time series. Thus, inaccurate estimates of equilibrium points with different slowdown periods can be constructed.

This may also lead to false corrections to the relationship in the long run.

Table (5): Showing the results of the optimal slowing down period for the study equation

SBIC	HQIC	AIC	FPE	p	Push	LR	FOR GIRLS	Lag
1.51866	1.45513	1.42525	.014258	-	-		-19.3788	0
-2.16216*	-2.35275	-2.4424	.000298	0.000	4	124.03	42.636	1
-2.12111	-2.43876*	-2.58818*	.000259*	0.015	4	12.373	48.8227	2

Source: Prepared by the researcher.

Note: The optimal lag period for the ADF test was selected based on Akaike standard information.

From the foregoing, it is noted that the results of the phenomenon in Table 5 show that the optimal degree of delay for the study equation and the agreement of the smallest value of the criteria is two lag periods (P = 2).

4.4 Structural break unit root test:

To overcome the low prediction power weakness of conventional unit root tests, especially in the presence of structural intervals, the non-static Zivot (1992) test was applied to the series in its levels and the first difference. The idea of "Zivot & Andrews", developed in 1996, was based on three equations, which included a pictorial variable for the year representing the structural segment in which the fluctuations of the fixed term appear in its three equations, in addition to another formal variable that represents the general direction of the structural variable.

Based on the above, the structural sections test was conducted for the "Zivot-Andrews" tests in order to ensure the presence of structural sections in the study or not, which may be the reason for not showing a balanced relationship between the study variables.

From the test results given in Table 2, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis of instability for all series at levels. Using this test, stability was achieved at the first difference variables, implying that all strings are complementary (1).

Table (6): Shows the results of the structural sections of the tests - "Zivot-Andrews"

variables variables	Zivot-Andrews test	Breakpoint	Tabular values of Z-A		
			1%	5%	10%
LGDPPC	**4.440-	2012	-5.34	-4.80	-4.58
LTC	-5.225**	2011	-534	-4.80	-4.58

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

The results of the "Zivot-Andrews" tests for structural sections showed the presence of more than one structural section among the study variables. The credit chain for the period 1990-2023 was found to contain a structural segment in 2012, and the GDP variable chain in the Libyan economy had a structural segment in 2011.

4.5 Joint integration in the style of "Gregory & Hansen":

Table 7: Results of Joint Integration in the Gregory & Hansen Style

Test	Statistical value	Break Point Structural section	Tabular values		
			1%	5%	10%
ADD	-5.68	2003	-5.13	-4.61	-4.34
Throw	-5.76	2003	-5.13	-4.61	-4.34
Za	-33.72	2003	-50.07	-40.48	-36.19

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

Based on the information mentioned in Table (7), the results of the relationship estimation using the "Johansen Co-integration" method are correct. We must take into account the effect of structural segments on the results of the long-term equilibrium relationship between time series associated with study variables. Long-term relationship estimation is questionable and its results cannot be relied upon without verifying the existence of the long-term relationship using the "Gregory & Hansen" co-integration methodology.

During the study period, Libya's economic policies witnessed significant changes in the overall structure of the economy. This has resulted in significant economic impacts shocks and repercussions on bank credit and GDP. As Libya is a country that relies mainly on income from oil exports, the impact of these structural changes has been reflected in data series related to the relationship between bank credit and GDP.

As a result of political and security instability in the Libyan economy during the study period, the structural variable "D" was added. Long-term relationships were estimated using Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Least Squares (DOLS) and Canonical Co-integrating methods.

Table (8): Results of long-term relationship estimation tests using "FMOLS, DOLS, & CCR

VARIABLES	Fully Modified Least Squares	(Dynamic Least Squares)	(Canonical Co-integrating Regression)
	(FOLMS)	(DOLS)	(CCR)
LTC	0.0424*** (.00831)	0.1998*** (.01739)	.1662*** (.00833)
D	-.30488*** (0.134)	-.62861*** (0.0525)	53184.- (0.213)
Constant	10.042***	8.1482***	9.002***
Observations	32	30	32
R-squared	0.390	0.382	0.0273

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program

From the previous analysis of Table (8), it can be seen that the results of estimating the relationship in the long term using the three methods showed that bank credit has statistical significance at a significant level of 1%.

The results presented in Table 6 indicate that the bank credit coefficient is statistically significant at a significant level of 1% in all estimation methods (FMOLS, DOLS and CCR). This means that credit has a long-term impact on GDP. The existence of a positive moral impact of credit on GDP, when the change in bank credit by one percentage output changes in the same direction by 0.0424, which is consistent with economic theory but the size of the impact is very small, it follows that credit has a long-term impact on GDP.

4.6 Granger Causality Tests:

Table 9: Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob
GDPPC does not Granger Cause TC	0.22895	0.6358
TC does not Granger Cause GDPPC	5.14816	0.0306

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the outputs of the STATA 15 program 15

The outputs of the estimation results according to Table (9) indicate a causal relationship compatible with the economic theory from credit (TC) to output (GDPPC).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The outputs of the estimation results of the Stata program according to Tables (8) and (2) indicate that there is a positive moral impact of credit on GDP, when bank credit changes by one percentage, the output changes in the same direction by 0.0424, which is consistent with economic theory, but the size of the impact is very small, it follows that credit has a long-term impact on GDP, but weak and this decrease in the relationship is due to the restrictions imposed by the Central Bank Commercial banks in granting credit as well as to the law to cancel usurious transactions in 2012.

The outputs of the estimation results according to Table (9) also indicate a causal relationship compatible with the economic theory from credit (TC) to output (GDPPC).

The result of the study was consistent with the study of Al-Hawij, Ahmed (2022), which found using the nonlinear self-distributed regression model (NARDL) that there is an effect of credit on economic growth and is weakly correlated. It was consistent with the study of Marzouk, and Abdul Razzaq (2023), which found a direct effect of credit on economic activity. It also concurred with the Malawi study, by Ahmed (2008) which found a positive effect of credit on economic activity using the VAR methodology. However the study differed from the study of Al-Tallawy, and Abdul Razzaq (2023), which found using the methodology of Angel Granger and causation that there is no long-term relationship between credit and economic activity, and the absence of a long-term impact between credit and growth due to the lack of successful credit policies from the Central Bank to commercial banks, and the same study reached a causal relationship according to economic theory from credit to growth.

Finally, it can be said that the results of the study were consistent with economic theory and the magnitude of previous studies.

Recommendations:

The need to work with a productive banking system, by directing bank credit to the productive sectors that contribute to increasing the domestic product and reducing consumer credit.

The need for monetary politicians to have an effective role in non-oil economic growth and support for small and medium enterprises enhances their growth.

Banks are restricted by laws and regulations that limit credit risks that oblige the bank to grant credit to the requested person based on the reports it submits and its previous reputation.

Regulators in the banking system must develop policies that promote access to credit for the private sector while containing inflation.

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Appendix (1)

GDP per capita (constant local currency) and GDP at constant prices during the period 1990-2023

Year	TC(million)	GDPPC(A)	GDP (billion)	Year	TC(million)	GDPPC(A)	GDP (billion)
1990	3053.3	16639.24	28904183602	2007	8191.3	20582.2	68032978391
1991	3152.3	18824.21	31991821265	2008	10544.6	20116.98	86710767415
1992	3392.2	17934.96	33887047909	2009	11812.7	18835.31	60808562033
1993	3710.2	16922.01	30660051911	2010	13044.6	19382.92	75380825062
1994	3986.1	16931.07	28610549763	2011	12786.6	9860.507	48169263294
1995	4281.5	16269.01	25541379187	2012	15899.5	18910.62	92540938129
1996	3915	16347.85	27884615385	2013	18232.3	15198.9	75351107029
1997	4165.9	16937.67	30700897875	2014	19959.9	11473.49	57372355592
1998	4530.2	16094.29	27251301398	2015	20212.9	11194.68	48717501321
1999	5203.6	15974.62	35975860857	2016	18770.3	10860.98	49912073701
2000	5584	16290.81	38270954138	2017	17446.7	14162.18	67157452182
2001	6057.6	15711.56	34112093927	2018	16448.3	15040.7	76686029772
2002	6357.8	15264.93	20481889764	2019	16912.8	13160.78	72081962263
2003	6775.1	16911.08	26265625000	2020	16996.9	9159.879	65688454972
2004	6510.3	17304.39	33122307692	2021	19637.5	11607.28	47786789104
2005	6166.6	18955.1	47334691241	2022	22970.9	10518.83	55938727098
2006	7067.2	19777.43	60094231607	2023	28510.4	11457.28	50491722446

Source: World Bank.

Source: Central Bank of Libya - Consolidated Balance Sheet of Commercial Banks.